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Robot arm training by image processing and reinforcement learning

MSC THESIS

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1 Introduction

In this thesis, I describe a robotic arm that I train to enable some tasks that include grasping an object. Firstly, I propose a system that enables a robotic arm to grasp a ball based on its camera image. My developed algorithm uses an OpenCV module (see, e.g., Bradski and Kaehler, 2008) and the YOLO algorithm ("You Only Look Once", Redmon et al., 2015) to detect the ball in the image and then calculates its position in a fixed global coordinate system of the robotic arm. This information is used to direct the movement of the robotic arm and enable it to grasp the ball.

My results show that my system is able to accurately detect and grasp the ball with high success rate. Overall, my system demonstrates the potential of using computer vision techniques to enable robots to perform complex tasks such as object grasping in real-world environments.

In my second, more complex task, my goal was to teach a robotic arm to build a tower of cubes starting from randomly positioned cubes on a table. I started to tackle this task by first training a robotic arm in a simulated environment. I use hierarchical reinforcement learning (see, Sutton and Barto, 1998, for an overview) in a sequence of desirable subtasks. Here high-level policies define the overall tower construction strategy, while low-level policies focus on subtasks, such as grasping, lifting and stacking the cubes. In the thesis I have developed the core theoretical framework of training the robotic arm using such subtasks and presented the optimization of policy parameters for one crucial subtask, namely reaching the cube. The policy of the reaching task was trained by the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm (PPO, Schulman et al., 2017). As an outlook to future work, I propose to similarly train all elementary subtasks and then to learn the hierarchical policy using these pre-trained low level policies.

Figure 1: QArm manipulator in its laboratory environment, in home position.

2 Description of the robotic arms

For my first task of grasping I used Quanser's QArm robot¹ whose parameters — described in Section 2.1 — were crucial in calculating the exact position of the ball.

The Quanser QArm is a four-degree-of-freedom robotic arm that is used for education and research in areas such as control systems, robotics, and mechatronics. The QArm is a compact and modular system that includes a base, four revolute joints, and an end-effector (see Fig. 1).

The QArm is controlled using its own software package that provides an interface for developing and testing control algorithms. The following notions and parameters related to the QArm are from the QArm User Manuals² and a more concise description comes from the Masters Thesis (Lestyán, 2021).

¹<https://www.quanser.com/products/qarm/>

²<https://quanserinc.box.com/shared/static/g5wnyugcvtzsa5rhceu033ehvddgubum>

Figure 2: Robosuite’s built-in Panda robot, a commercially-available manipulator model, in its simulation environment. One can choose and specify the details of the robotic simulation: the Robot Models (e.g., Panda, Sawyer, Baxter), the Object Models (e.g., cubes), and the Arena (table, for instance).

The QArm consists of four joints as mentioned before, the base, shoulder, elbow, and wrist joints, and it also uses a two-finger gripper, which can grasp objects. The first three joints determine the end-effector’s position and the last joint orients the gripper, so the wrist angle does not affect the position of the end-effector. The home position of the manipulator and its link lengths are shown in Figure 3 and its parameters in Table 1.

With the given length parameters, the manipulator has a net horizontal reach of 0.7536 meters. The net vertical reach stands at 0.8936 meters due to the added height from the base. The joint specifications are shown in Table 2.

For the second task of building a tower of cubes I use a simulated environment, using the Robosuite simulation framework powered by the MuJoCo physics engine for robot learning (Zhu et al., 2020), and the therein predefined robotic arm and its simulation environment called Panda. The goal is to replace in the future the Panda robotic arm to the simulation model the

Figure 3: Geometry and joint configuration of the Quanser's QArm manipulator in home pose.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
L_1	0.14 m	L_4	0.25 m
L_2	0.35 m	L_5	0.15 m
L_3	0.05 m	β	8.13°

Table 1: Parameters of the QArm

QArm, however the development of the dynamic simulation environment in the Robosuite framework of the robotic arm extend the limits of this thesis work.

The Robosuite environment uses the Mujoco physics engine (Todorov et al., 2012) as mentioned, which provides an environment with rather realistic physical rules in which the cubes and robot arm can interact with each other.

2.1 Parameters of the QArm

In Figure 3, I display the parameters that are also listed in Table 1. The values L_i are the length of the different parts and β is a given angle. I give more detail about β below.

Note that the manipulator shown in Figures 1 and 3 is currently in its home position. In this state, the joint space vector θ takes the following values:

$$\theta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \beta - \frac{\pi}{2} \\ -\beta \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

The manipulator is precisely calibrated to correspond to this specific position. Consequently, if an actuator command of $[0, 0, 0, 0]$ is executed, the manipulator will return to its initial position, commonly known as the home position. In this configuration, the encoders will detect a joint position of $[0, 0, 0, 0]$ as well.

To eliminate the need for constantly accounting for the offset in equation (1), an alternate joint space can be introduced denoted as ϕ . By employing a mapping outlined in Table 3, The manipulator can be conveniently described using ϕ space and performing the necessary mathematical operations in this space. This approach simplifies the process and enables to work with the manipulator's representation more effectively.

For example, a command of $\phi_2 = 0$ will imply $\theta_2 = \beta - \frac{\pi}{2}$, which corresponds to joint 2 in the home position.

Table 2 shows the limits of the joints' angle and speed.

Item	Min. joint	Max. joint	Max.speed	Max. acceleration
Base	-170°	$+170^\circ$	$\pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ rad/s	$\pm\frac{\pi}{3}$ rad/s/s
Shoulder	-85°	$+85^\circ$	$\pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ rad/s	$\pm\frac{\pi}{3}$ rad/s/s
Elbow	-95°	$+75^\circ$	$\pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ rad/s	$\pm\frac{\pi}{3}$ rad/s/s
Wrist	-160°	$+160^\circ$	$\pm\frac{\pi}{2}$ rad/s	$\pm\frac{\pi}{3}$ rad/s/s
Gripper	0%	100%	$\pm 100\%$	$\pm 400\%$

Table 2: Value restrictions

New parameter	Original parameter	New parameter	Original parameter
λ_1	L_1	ϕ_1	θ_1
λ_2	$\sqrt{L_2^2 + L_3^2}$	ϕ_2	$\theta_2 + \frac{\pi}{2} - \beta$
λ_3	$L_4 + L_5$	ϕ_3	$\theta_3 + \beta$
β	$\tan^{-1}(\frac{L_3}{L_2})$	ϕ_4	θ_4

Table 3: Linear mapping

2.2 Position space and joint space

Upon reviewing the parameters, my next step is to delve into the kinematics of the manipulator. However, before proceeding, it is important to define two distinct coordinate systems, the position space and the joint space, for the description of the robotic arm state.

With a control algorithm defined in the position space, the user has the ability to provide a three-dimensional vector that describes the desired position of the arm's end-effector in an Euclidean coordinate system, defined by the mutually perpendicular coordinate axes (x,y and z). The origin of the coordinate system is at the "base" point of the arm. In this case the origin of the coordinate system is the base of the arm. Accordingly, the coordinate of the base defined in the position space is defined by

$$b_p = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

In this coordinate system I can give the end-effector's coordinates:

$$e_p = \begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \\ z_e \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Here b_p is the position of the base and e_p is the position of the end-effector and also x_e, y_e, z_e are its defining coordinates.

In joint space, the state of the robotic arm can be given by a four-dimensional vector, where each coordinate is a rotation angle of the joints. The home position of the robotic arm is given by

$$h_j = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The position of the robotic arm is given by

$$\theta_j = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \\ \theta_4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Here θ_1 is the rotation of the base joint in radian, θ_2 is the rotation of the shoulder joint etc.

Forward kinematics and inverse kinematics are both concepts in robotics Kucuk and Bingul (2006) and computer graphics that describe how to calculate the position and orientation of an object in space. Forward kinematics maps from the joint space state to the position space, computing from the joint

rotations the coordinates of the end-effector. If the position of the end-effector (e_p) was given, the rotations (θ_j) can be computed by the map of the inverse kinematics, computing the rotations θ_j from the position of the end effector, e_p . The robotic arm is controlled by giving the exact joint rotations (the desired position in the rotation space). However, if I wish to control instead the coordinate of the end effector, I need to use the inverse kinematics. It is easy to see that one position can belong to more than one vector of rotations. The robot arm's software is written in a way that it uses the closest solution to the current position.

The forward kinematics process is relatively straightforward and can be calculated using simple trigonometric functions dependent on the Denavit-Hartenberg parameters.

DH parameters, or Denavit-Hartenberg parameters (Denavit and Hartenberg, 1955; Hartenberg and Denavit, 1964), are a set of four parameters assigned to each joint of a robotic arm. The four parameters are:

- Link length (a): The distance between the two adjacent joint axes along the common normal.
- Link twist (α): The angle between the previous joint axis and the current joint axis, measured about their common normal.
- Link offset (d): The distance between the two adjacent joint axes along the previous joint axis.
- Joint angle (θ): The angle between the previous link and the current link, measured about the current joint axis.

In Table 4, I show the DH parameters that the kinematics use.

DH parameters are a convention used in robotics to describe the kinematics of robotic arms with multiple joints. For a robotic arm with n joints, n coordinate frames are defined, and each joint is assigned four DH parameters

i	a_i	α_i	d_i	θ_i
1	0	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$	λ_1	θ_1
2	0	0	0	θ_2
3	0	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$	0	θ_3
4	0	0	λ_3	θ_4

Table 4: DH table

$(a_i, \alpha_i, d_i, \theta_i)$ that describe the relationship between adjacent links and their corresponding joints.

The DH parameters are used to construct transformation matrices that relate the coordinate frames of adjacent links. The overall transformation matrix from the base frame to the end-effector frame is obtained by multiplying the individual transformation matrices for each joint.

The resulting matrix describes the position and orientation of the end-effector of the robotic arm with respect to the base frame. DH transformations (Denavit and Hartenberg, 1955; Hartenberg and Denavit, 1964) are widely used in robotics and provide a convenient and consistent method for describing the kinematics of robotic arms. In this thesis, I do not describe the forward kinematics in detail as it is beyond the scope of my study.

Inverse kinematics (Karlik and Aydin, 2000) refers to the process of determining the angles of the joints that will position the end-effector in a specific location and orientation. It is important because it allows to control the motion of the robotic arm in a way that is intuitive to humans, such as by specifying the desired position and orientation of the end-effector. The tricky part is that the inverse kinematics is not a well-posed problem, and several different rotation combinations may correspond to the same end effector position.

DH transformations are used in inverse kinematics to compute the joint angles required to achieve a desired end-effector position and orientation. Inverse kinematics is discussed further in Section 3.4.

3 Catching an object in real-world example

My goal is to catch different types of objects with the robotic arm. First of all, I need to know the coordinates of the object in the position space (also called real world coordinates). My first object is a blue ball; a regular stress ball, more precisely.

3.1 Positioning the ball in the image

For determining the position of the ball, I used two methods, a YOLO-based object detection (Redmon et al., 2015), and certain OpenCV (Bradski and Kaehler, 2008) resources.

The YOLO-based detection finds the ball and frames it (with a rectangle) (see Fig. 4) with high success rate, but with the limitation that I gain no information on the size of the ball. Even with this limited information, the robotic arm is capable of following the ball by turning to the direction of the labelled frame. By following the ball, I can turn the camera to the right angle to catch the ball later, because in practice my calculations are more accurate when the ball is near the center of the image.

By using OpenCV resources, I can detect the exact shape of the ball within the labelling frame (see Fig. 5). By fitting a circle, I obtain the pixel coordinates of the center point and the radius in pixel. Then, I use these parameters to calculate the real world coordinates.

3.2 Determining depth

By using one RGB camera only, it is difficult to determine the depth of an object. I overcome the limitation of the single camera by collecting data from known distances about the ball's visible size and then use a simple regression task to fit a function to the data to infer the distance in an unknown scenario.

Figure 4: Object (blue ball) detection with the YOLO algorithm (Redmon et al., 2015), after which the object can be followed with the robotic arm, i.e., the ball gets re-centered in the image in an iterative manner. The YOLO-predicted confidence score of the ball is also given.

When the camera captures an approximate shape of the ball, I fit a circle to obtain the radius and approximate the distance by the function obtained by regression.

I have tape-measured the distance of the ball in several positions along a perpendicular line to the image plane, from the back of the camera box to the front face of the blue ball. I obtained radius estimates of two ball-detecting methods: a blob detection, and the `cv2.HOUGH_CIRCLES()` function.

The size (or radius, R) of the object is inversely proportional to the distance of the ball from the camera (D), $R \propto 1/D$. Thus, it can be assumed that $R \times D$ gives a constant:

$$R = \frac{c}{D} \quad \rightarrow \quad c = RD.$$

Though we were experimenting with different approximation to compute

Figure 5: For grasping the blue ball with the two-finger gripper, I have identified the global coordinates of the ball from the camera coordinates *and* I have also better calibrated the distance to the object. The arm can reach and grab the ball after the center position and shape are detected with OpenCV’s Hough Circle function yielding the white dot and the yellow circle, respectively. The red dot represents the detected ball center with a simple blob detection method, given as comparison.

Figure 6: **Left:** Average of R_{BlobDet} and $R_{\text{HoughCirc}}$ (per measurement points) multiplied by D in the function of D . The mean of the above averages (i.e., the constant) is 2788.3. **Right:** Both R_{BD} and R_{HC} radii plotted per measurement points. The blue fit is given by a quadratic polynomial to the average of the two radii, as used in the left panel, and the red fit represents the function constant/ x .

D from the radius R of the framing circle in the image, the most sensible and exact approximation is this inversely proportional dependence. (see Fig. 6).

3.3 Transformation from image coordinates and depth to world coordinates

After I have two pixel coordinates of the detected circle center point and depth, I can determine the 3D coordinates of the ball. The computation also relies on the robotic arm's current state. From the pixel coordinates and depth I can compute the ball position in the camera coordinate system, the coordinate system tied to the focus point of the camera. After that, I transform the camera coordinate system into the coordinate system shifted to the end-effector. Finally, I determine the coordinates in the position space.

The first step in this process is to detect the ball in the camera image using OpenCV³. Once the ball is detected, its position in the camera image can be represented using image coordinates, which are the pixel coordinates of the ball within the image.

However, in order to calculate the position of the ball in the 3D coordinates of the robotic arm, I also need to know the distance of the ball from the camera by using the depth information.

The resulting 3D position of the ball is in the camera coordinate system, which is not the same as the coordinate system of the robotic arm. Therefore, I need to perform a transformation to convert the ball's position from the camera coordinate system to the coordinate system of the robotic arm's end effector and then to the global coordinate system. For the depth D estimation I used the above described approximation.

Once the transformation is performed, I have the position of the ball in

³For calibrating the parameters of the built-in camera of the robotic arm, I have followed the steps at https://docs.opencv.org/4.x/dc/dbb/tutorial_py_calibration.html

the coordinate system of the robotic arm, which can be used to control the movement of the arm to grasp the ball.

Coordinate system notations

- $\vec{x} = [x, y, z]^T$: Coordinates in the global coordinate system (fixed to the base of the robotic arm, (x pointing forward, y pointing left, z pointing upward))
- $\vec{x}_c = [x_c, y_c, z_c]^T$: Coordinates in the coordinate system fixed to the focal point of the camera (computed by the parameters of the camera calibrated; x_c pointing left, y_c pointing upward, z_c pointing forward)
- x_e, y_e, z_e : Coordinates in the coordinate system fixed to the end-effector (that I can get with the help of a transformation matrix \vec{T} from the forward kinematics function, x_e pointing upward, y_e pointing right, z_e pointing forward)

The lower index shows the type of the coordinate system, while the upper index is the abbreviation of the object, for example $\vec{x}_c^{(b)}$ is the coordinate of the ball in the coordinate system fixed to the camera, $\vec{x}^{(\text{eff})}$ is the coordinate of the end-effector in the global coordinate system.

Coordinate transformations It is possible to get the global coordinates \vec{x} of a given point, if I know its coordinates tied to the end-effector \vec{x}_e . This map is given by the $\vec{T} = \vec{T}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ transformation matrix of shape 4x4, where the upper left corner of the matrix is the rotational matrix \vec{R} and the first three elements of the last column are the coordinates of the end-effector $\vec{x}^{(\text{eff})}$ given in the global coordinate system:

$$\vec{T} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{R} & \vec{x}^{\text{eff}} \\ \vec{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \vec{T} \begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \\ z_e \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Assumptions. Let's first assume that the coordinates \vec{x}_e of a point can be easily computed by

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \\ z_e \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{R}_{ce}} \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ y_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ s_3 \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{s}}, \quad (8)$$

where s_1 , s_2 , and s_3 are some unknown shifts from the camera's fixed point to the end effector. Rearranging the equation, I get the unknown shifts:

$$\vec{s} = \vec{x}_e - \vec{R}_{ce}\vec{x}_c \quad (9)$$

Calibration. To find the three shift values, I repeat the following four steps at least 10 times, and store for each round of the loop the values of the shift \vec{s} and the coordinates $\vec{x}_e^{(b)}$ and $\vec{x}_c^{(b)}$.

1. Locate the ball at a known global position $\vec{x}^{(b)}$
 - Choose an arbitrary rotation $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(b)}$ of the robotic arm
 - Compute and store $\vec{x}^{(b)}$ from the forward kinematics function F ,

$$\vec{x}^{(b)} = F(\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(b)}) \quad (10)$$

- Move the robotic arm with rotations $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{(b)}$ and open its gripper
- Place the ball in the position of the end-effector

- Move back the robotic arm to home position
2. Move the robotic arm to a position where the placed ball is visible to the camera and compute the position of the ball in the coordinate fixed to the end-effector, $\vec{x}_e^{(b)}$.
 - From the rotations $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, corresponding to this new position of the robotic arm, compute the transformation matrix $\vec{T}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$
 - Compute and store the coordinate of the ball $\vec{x}_e^{(b)}$ from eq. (7), that is

$$\vec{x}_e^{(b)} = \vec{T}(\boldsymbol{\theta})^{-1} \vec{x}^{(b)} \quad (11)$$

3. Run the ball finder code, get and store the coordinate of the ball in the coordinate system fixed to the camera, $\vec{x}_c^{(b)}$
4. Compute and store the difference \vec{s} between the two coordinates (from eq. (9)), that is

$$\vec{s} = \vec{x}_e^{(b)} - \vec{R}_{ce} \vec{x}_c^{(b)}, \quad (12)$$

where the rotation matrix \vec{R}_{ce} is shown in eq. (8)

When the values \vec{s} are evaluated for the different ball and camera positions, I compute the average of the shifts and decide whether my assumptions were valid by computing the variance of the shifts. The conclusion was that it didn't differ much, and the fact that the arm could catch the ball based on this calculations also proves that the estimations were right.

Remark: after the first cycle of the loop, the first step can be skipped, I can make a few evaluations of the coordinates by only moving the robotic arm and not the ball, which makes the evaluation faster.

3.4 Catching the object using inverse kinematics

As I transformed the data coming from the image, I can now use inverse kinematics to move the robot arm to the desired position. For this purpose, I further discuss the inverse kinematics framework.

The Denavit-Hartenberg parameters (Denavit and Hartenberg, 1955; Hartenberg and Denavit, 1964) are a set of four parameters assigned to each joint of a robotic arm. The four parameters are:

- Link length (a): The distance between the two adjacent joint axes along the common normal.
- Link twist (α): The angle between the previous joint axis and the current joint axis, measured about their common normal.
- Link offset (d): The distance between the two adjacent joint axes along the previous joint axis.
- Joint angle (θ): The angle between the previous link and the current link, measured about the current joint axis.

To compute the inverse kinematics of a robotic arm, I first calculate the transformation matrix from the base frame to the end-effector frame using the DH parameters. I can then use the elements of this matrix to derive the equations that relate the joint angles to the end-effector position and orientation.

In detail I would like a function that gives back the value of θ :

$$\theta = f(e_p) \tag{13}$$

The transformation matrices are at the case of a QArm:

$${}^0T_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_1 & 0 & -\sin \theta_1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta_1 & 0 & \cos \theta_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & \lambda_1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$${}^1T_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_2 & -\sin \theta_2 & 0 & \lambda_2 \cos \theta_2 \\ \sin \theta_2 & \cos \theta_2 & 0 & \lambda_2 \sin \theta_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$${}^2T_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_3 & 0 & -\sin \theta_3 & 0 \\ \sin \theta_3 & 0 & \cos \theta_3 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$${}^3T_4 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_4 & -\sin \theta_4 & 0 & 0 \\ \sin \theta_4 & \cos \theta_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \lambda_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

From forward kinematics I know that

$$p_x = \lambda_2 \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \lambda_3 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 \theta_3 \quad (18)$$

$$p_y = \lambda_2 \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 - \lambda_3 \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 \theta_3 \quad (19)$$

Then I take these two equations and calculate the sum of their squares:

$$p_x^2 + p_y^2 = \cos^2 \theta_1 (\lambda_2 \cos \theta_2 - \lambda_3 \sin \theta_2 \theta_3)^2 + \sin^2 \theta_1 (\lambda_2 \cos \theta_2 - \lambda_3 \sin \theta_2 \theta_3)^2 \quad (20)$$

From which the following comes:

$$\sqrt{p_x^2 + p_y^2} = \lambda_2 \cos \theta_2 - \lambda_3 \sin \theta_2 \theta_3 \quad (21)$$

And I know that:

$$\lambda_1 - p_z = \lambda_2 \sin \theta_2 + \lambda_3 \cos \theta_2 \theta_3 \quad (22)$$

I take the following mapping:

$$A = \lambda_2, B = 0, C = -\lambda_3, D = \pm \sqrt{p_x^2 + p_y^2}, \quad (23)$$

$$H = \lambda_1 - p_z, q_1 = \theta_2, q_2 = \theta_3, F = \frac{D^2 + H^2 - A^2 - C^2}{2A} \quad (24)$$

$$M = A + C \sin(q_2), N = -C \cos(q_2), \quad (25)$$

$$\cos(q_1) = \frac{DM + HN}{M^2 + N^2}, \sin(q_1) = \frac{H - N \cos(q_1)}{M} \quad (26)$$

Finally, the following formulas describe my equations:

$$A \cos(q_1) + B \cos(q_1 + q_2) + C \sin(q_1 + q_2) = D \quad (27)$$

$$A \sin(q_1) + B \sin(q_1 + q_2) - C \cos(q_1 + q_2) = H \quad (28)$$

The solutions for θ_3 are from these equations (note that $\theta_3 = q_2$):

$$\theta_3^1 = 2 \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{C \pm \sqrt{C^2 + F^2}}{F} \right) \quad (29)$$

The solution for θ_2 (note that $\theta_2 = q_1$):

$$\theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin(q_1)}{\cos(q_1)} \right) \quad (30)$$

I omit the detailed discussion on how to calculate θ_1 , and all possible values for $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ from the above angles. Obtaining θ_4 is trickier, because it cannot be determined from the end-effector position as it only gives the orientation of the end-effector. Often it's enough to just guess a value for θ_4 .

4 Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a branch of machine learning that focuses on training agents to make sequential decisions in dynamic environments. Unlike supervised learning, which relies on labeled data, and unsupervised learning, which seeks to uncover hidden patterns, reinforcement learning emphasizes learning through interaction and feedback. For an overview on RL, see Sutton and Barto (1998).

In reinforcement learning, an agent interacts with an environment and learns to take actions to maximize a cumulative reward signal. The agent receives feedback in the form of rewards based on the quality of its actions. The ultimate objective is for the agent to learn an optimal policy, which is a mapping from states to actions that maximizes the expected cumulative reward over time.

The agent explores the environment through a trial-and-error process, trying different actions and observing their consequences. It learns from the feedback received after each action, updating its knowledge and adjusting its behavior accordingly. Over time, the agent's policy evolves as it discovers more effective strategies for achieving higher rewards.

Reinforcement learning has gained significant attention due to its appli-

cability in various domains, including robotics, game playing, finance, and healthcare. It has demonstrated remarkable achievements in complex tasks, such as playing complex games like Go and Chess at a superhuman level, controlling autonomous vehicles, and optimizing resource allocation in dynamic environments.

Here I focus on the reinforcement learning algorithm called Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO). PPO (Schulman et al., 2017) is a policy optimization algorithm that balances between performance and comprehensibility. Empirically, it demonstrates competitiveness with high-quality benchmarks, and in certain tasks, it surpasses them by a significant margin. Additionally, PPO's strength lies in its simplicity, making it accessible and practical for adoption by a diverse user base, a characteristic not shared by every algorithm in the realm of reinforcement learning.

I will briefly discuss the main points of policy gradient methods, natural policy gradients, and Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO, Schulman et al., 2015), which together form the stepping stones towards PPO. For more details on PPO, see, for instance, Schulman et al. (2017); Bick (2021). On evaluating different versions of model-free policy gradient methods, I refer the reader to Riedmiller et al. (2007). Throughout the studies, as well as here, the materials given by (van Heeswijk, 2022) proved quite useful for understanding.

4.1 Vanilla policy gradient

The concept behind reinforcement learning revolves around the objective of acquiring an effective decision-making policy π that maximizes cumulative rewards over time. In this context, a policy π is essentially a function that returns an action a based on the problem's state s , denoted as $\pi : s \rightarrow a$. Policy-based methods employ a function, often implemented as a neural network, characterized by a parameter set θ . By iteratively adjusting these

parameters, observing the resulting changes in rewards, and updating θ in the direction that leads to higher rewards, it can establish the foundation for all policy gradient methods (e.g., Williams, 1992).

The policy $\pi_\theta(a|s)$ exhibits a stochastic nature, indicating that the parameters θ dictate the sampling probability of actions a , consequently shaping the probability of the following trajectories $\tau = s_1, a_1, \dots, s_n, a_n$. Hence, I can establish an objective function that relies on the parameter θ as follows:

$$J(\theta) = E_{\tau \sim \pi_\theta} R(\tau) = \sum_{\tau} P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau), \quad (31)$$

where each trajectory τ has a corresponding probability of $P(\tau, \theta)$ depending on the actual θ , and a cumulative reward $R(\tau) = \sum_{t=1}^n \gamma^t R_t$.

My goal is to maximize this objective function. While I have a grasp on computing the reward component, the probability aspect needs further calculations and considerations.

$$P(\tau; \theta) = \prod_{t=0}^n P(s_{t+1}|s_t, a_t) \cdot \pi_\theta(a_t|s_t) \quad (32)$$

Given the stochastic nature of the policy, I sample various actions, each associated with corresponding probabilities, allowing to measure differences in rewards. To identify the direction for updating the parameters that enhance the objective function, policy gradient methods utilize gradients ∇_θ (a vector of derivatives). Consequently, the update function can be expressed as follows:

$$\theta \rightarrow \theta + \alpha \nabla_\theta J(\theta) \quad (33)$$

4.1.1 Deriving the policy gradient

In order to obtain an explicit gradient of the objective function, let's discuss the process step by step. To begin, let's consider taking the gradient of the

expected rewards

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \nabla_{\theta} E_{\tau \sim \pi_{\theta}} R(\tau) = \nabla_{\theta} \sum_{\tau} P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau). \quad (34)$$

The gradient of a sum equals the sum of gradients, thus I can move the gradient within the summation, that is,

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \sum_{\tau} \nabla_{\theta} P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau). \quad (35)$$

By multiplying with $1 = \frac{P(\tau; \theta)}{P(\tau; \theta)}$, the following equation can be obtained

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \sum_{\tau} \frac{P(\tau; \theta)}{P(\tau; \theta)} \cdot \nabla_{\theta} P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau), \quad (36)$$

and this can be rewritten (36) as

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \sum_{\tau} P(\tau; \theta) \frac{\nabla_{\theta} P(\tau; \theta)}{P(\tau; \theta)} R(\tau). \quad (37)$$

Since the following stands,

$$\frac{\nabla_{\theta} P(\tau; \theta)}{P(\tau; \theta)} = \nabla_{\theta} \log P(\tau; \theta), \quad (38)$$

I can rewrite the gradient to

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \sum_{\tau} P(\tau; \theta) \nabla_{\theta} \log P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau). \quad (39)$$

First, I perform the log transformation and compute the sum of gradients of the probabilities. Next, I sum over the probabilities to rewrite the gradient expression as an expectation. Consequently, the final step can be represented

as

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi_\theta} \nabla_\theta \log P(\tau; \theta) R(\tau). \quad (40)$$

To obtain the gradient, the $P(\tau; \theta)$ needs to be calculated by

$$\nabla_\theta \log P(\tau; \theta) = \nabla_\theta \log \left[\prod_{t=0}^n P(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t) \cdot \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \right]. \quad (41)$$

Based on logarithmic identities the right hand side can be rewritten

$$\nabla_\theta \left[\sum_{t=0}^n \log P(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t) + \sum_{t=0}^n \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \right]. \quad (42)$$

It becomes evident that the first part within the gradient is not dependent on the parameter θ . Therefore, it can be left out from my calculations, simplifying the expression by

$$\nabla_\theta J(\theta) = \nabla_\theta \sum_{t=0}^n \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t). \quad (43)$$

As a final step, I bring the gradient sign inside the summation. The final result for the gradient reads

$$\nabla_\theta J(\theta) = \sum_{t=0}^n \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t). \quad (44)$$

4.1.2 Approximating the gradient

Unfortunately, the computations I have performed so far involve the true expectation, considering all possible trajectories. Typical RL problems are computationally intractable, since otherwise just applying Dynamic Programming would suffice, so I need to approximate by using a sample of trajectories.

To compute an approximate gradient, I rely on a finite set of samples. Since I have already established that the gradient is an expectation, it can be

estimated by using simulation. The expression for the estimated gradient is

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) \approx g = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \nabla_{\theta} \log P(\tau^{(i)}; \theta) R(\tau^{(i)}) \quad (45)$$

In this expression, $\tau^{(i)}$ represents the i th trajectory. The great advantage of this formulation is its tractability. I can sample the trajectories and their associated rewards without requiring knowledge of the complete environment model. All that is necessary is an explicitly defined policy that is differentiable with respect to θ .

4.1.3 Defining the update rule

After computing the approximate gradient, the next step is to apply it to update the policy. The objective is to gradually adjust the policy parameters based on the sampled observations. To accomplish this, a learning rate $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is introduced, which determines the weight assigned to the computed gradient to update the current parameter vector. The update rule can be expressed by

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta + \underbrace{\alpha \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)}_{\Delta \theta}. \quad (46)$$

Often the update rule is denoted by the $\Delta \theta$ with which θ would change, by $\Delta \theta = \alpha \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)$.

I have a reward signal and an update direction now but do not exactly know how much the policy should be updated. In the realm of policy gradient, problems related to selecting the appropriate learning rate α can arise.

Due to the risk of large policy changes, samples are only used once. After that, the policy is updated, and the updated policy is employed to generate another trajectory sample. This process can be inefficient, particularly when sampling is computationally expensive. Furthermore, the old samples may

become less representative after a substantial policy update.

Another issue is inconsistent policy updates. In some cases, policy updates may overshoot and miss the optimal reward, or they may stall prematurely. This problem is particularly common in neural network architectures, where challenges such as vanishing or exploding gradients can occur. If a bad update occurs, the algorithm may struggle to recover and improve further.

4.2 Natural policy gradients

Natural policy gradients (e.g., Kakade, 2001) offer a solution to the challenge of selecting suitable learning rates. To do so, the method embeds second-order derivatives that quantify how sensitive the gradient is when updating weights. For understanding and explaining, the explanation by (Van Heeswijk, 2022) was used.

The Kullback-Leibner (KL) divergence measures how much a policy π_θ changes due to an update. Remember that the policy is represented by a probability distribution, which determines the probability of selecting a specific action. KL divergence is defined by

$$\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\pi_\theta || \pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}) = \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \pi_\theta(x) \log \left(\frac{\pi_\theta(x)}{\pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}(x)} \right). \quad (47)$$

Here π_θ is the former policy and $\Delta\theta$ represents the change in this policy.

If I restrict the divergence of the update to be no more than ϵ , weights can be updated using the formula

$$\Delta\theta^* = \arg \max_{\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\pi_\theta || \pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}) \leq \epsilon} J(\theta + \Delta\theta), \quad (48)$$

where J is the objective function discussed in the previous chapter.

The scheme described above is not applicable in practice, since reinforce-

ment learning operates with sampled observations. To include the KL divergence, a Taylor expansion on the modified objective function is used. A first-order expansion is performed on the objective itself, while a second-order expansion on the KL divergence. After some mathematical efforts, the following update formula is obtained:

$$\Delta\theta = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon}{\Delta J(\theta)^T F(\theta)^{-1} \Delta J(\theta)}} \Delta J(\theta), \quad (49)$$

where the $F(\theta)^{-1}$ is the inverse of the Fisher information matrix.

In summary, the learning rate α has been replaced with a dynamic learning rate, depending on local sensitivity of the objective function. This sensitivity is represented by the Fisher information matrix $F(\theta)$. When implemented, the natural gradient update formula enables larger updates in insensitive regions and smaller ones in curved regions (e.g., close to reward peaks).

In theory, natural gradients (e.g., Amari, 1998) allow stable updates with appropriate step sizes. Due to restricting the volume by which the policy changes, samples could be re-used more than once, enhancing sample efficiency. However, in practice, natural gradient method exhibits several shortcomings:

- High computational cost $O(N^3)$ of inverting the Fisher matrix F . Given that neural networks frequently consist thousands of parameters, this is often restrictive. Additionally, the inversion may fail due to numerical instabilities introduced by the approximations made.
- The KL-constraint might not be satisfied. The Taylor expansions are only an approximation of the theoretical objective function. As such, the analytically derived step size can be too large and still have overshooting behavior.

4.3 Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO)

I describe two key components of the TRPO (Schulman et al., 2015) algorithm that I require in my experiments. For understanding, the explanation by (Van Heeswijk, 2022) was used again. First, the surrogate advantage $\mathcal{L}_{\pi_\theta}(\pi_\theta + \Delta\theta)$ coming from importance sampling reflects the expected advantage of an update as

$$J(\pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}) - J(\pi_\theta) \approx \mathbf{E}_{s \sim \rho_{\pi_\theta}} \frac{\pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}(a|s)}{\pi_\theta(a|s)} A^{\pi_\theta}(s, a) = \mathcal{L}_{\pi_\theta}(\pi_\theta + \Delta\theta) \quad (50)$$

where the $A^{\pi_\theta}(s, a)$ is called the advantage which indicates for a specific policy π and a state s the expected reward for an action a minus the overall expected value. The expression ρ_{π_θ} is the state distribution corresponding to the current policy.

The disadvantage of the theoretical TRPO approach is the rather small updates and slow convergence. Therefore the practical TRPO algorithm is different from the theoretical one in some significant points. It is important to distinguish between the theoretical model of TRPO (penalty-based) and the practical implementation (constraint-based).

Specifically, the practical implementation of TRPO improves upon natural gradient methods with the next three adjustments:

- Conjugate gradient method. The natural policy gradients computations only require the product $F^{-1}\nabla \log \pi_\theta(x)$ and not the inverse matrix itself. Conjugate gradients can approximate this product much faster than matrix inversion could, greatly speeding up the updating.
- Line search. Due to simplifications, the analytical step size derived for natural policy gradients might violate the KL-divergence limit. TRPO starts with the originally suggested step size, but measures whether

the divergence constraint is not violated after the update. If it is, it iteratively and exponentially reduces the trust region (using a reducing parameter α^j) until the divergence constraint is met.

- Improvement enforcement. The update are required to improve the policy. TRPO acknowledges this problem by actually verifying whether the surrogate loss $\mathcal{L}(\theta)$ improves after the update, prior to accepting it. Not that due of approximations, theoretical guarantees do no longer hold.

TRPO manages a number of problems coming from natural policy gradients. However, a number of disadvantages remains, in particular:

- Inability to handle large parameter matrices. Despite applying the conjugate gradient method, large Fisher matrices still can be a problem, even when they don't need to be inverted. Unfortunately, deep neural networks contain many parameters, and accurately approximating F requires large numbers of samples.
- Second-order optimization is slow. The practical implementation of TRPO is constraint-based and requires to compute previously mentioned Fisher matrix, which significantly slows down the updating procedure.
- TRPO is complicated. TRPO is quite hard to explain, implement and debug. When training does not give back the desired results, it can be tricky to figure out how to improve performance. As such, it isn't the most user-friendly reinforcement learning algorithm.

4.4 Proximal Policy Optimization

There are two main variants of PPO that I discuss in this thesis: PPO Penalty and PPO Clip. I will first look at penalty-based version, which is a lit-

tle closer to TRPO. For understanding and explaining, the explanation by (Van Heeswijk, 2022) was used again.

4.4.1 Variant with Adaptive KL Penalty

The theoretical TRPO involves KL divergence as a soft penalty, as seen in the previous section, yet the actual implementation is constraint-based. The theoretical TRPO analytically derives a penalty to multiply with the divergence, yet in practice this penalty is often overly limiting, creating only very small updates. Therefore the question is how to determine an appropriate scaling parameter β that allows larger updates, yet avoids large drifts:

$$\Delta\theta^* = \arg \max_{\Delta\theta} [\mathcal{L}_{\theta+\Delta\theta}(\theta + \Delta\theta) - \beta(\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\pi_{\theta}||\pi_{\theta+\Delta\theta}))]. \quad (51)$$

The problem with this expression is that it is very difficult to determine a concrete value for β that can work for multiple problem settings. Even for the same problem characteristics may change over time. As hard thresholds aren't placed on divergence, sometimes it's punished more severely than other times.

PPO sets a 'target divergence' δ ; and I would like my updates to be somewhere close to this divergence. The target divergence should be large enough to significantly alter the policy, but small enough for updates to be stable.

After each update, PPO looks at the size of the update. If the realized divergence exceeds the target divergence by more than 1.5 (it can be changed, but the default value is 1.5), for the next iteration divergence should be penalized harder by doubling β . The other way around, I halve β if updates are too small, effectively expanding the trust region. Note that you can see some similarities with TRPO's line search here, yet the PPO search works in both

directions.

Algorithm 1 PPO with Adaptive KL Penalty

- 1: **Input:** initial policy parameters θ_0 , initial KL penalty β_0 , target KL-divergence δ
- 2: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
- 3: Collect set of partial trajectories \mathcal{D}_k on policy $\pi_k = \pi(\theta_k)$
- 4: Estimate advantages A^{π_k} using any advantage estimation algorithm
- 5: Compute policy update

$$\theta_{k+1} = \arg \max_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\theta_k}(\theta) - \beta_k \mathcal{D}_{KL}(\theta || \theta_k)$$

- 6: by taking K steps of minibatch SGD (via Adam)
 - 7: **if** $\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\theta || \theta_k) \geq 1.5\delta$ **then**
 - 8: $\beta_{k+1} = 2\beta_k$
 - 9: **else if** $\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\theta || \theta_k) < 1.5\delta$ **then**
 - 10: $\beta_{k+1} = \frac{\beta_k}{2}$
-

Note that target threshold is determined heuristically without theoretical background.. The constraint might be violated, but can be corrected by adjusting β . In summary, in favor of faster convergence some mathematical background can be sacrificed.

The outline for the penalty-based variant of PPO is detailed at Algorithm 1. Note it is fairly similar to the theoretical model of TRPO, but uses some heuristic approximations to make it practically applicable as well.

As PPO updates are fairly small, it is possible to limitedly re-use generated samples. PPO implementations often use early stopping when exceeding a certain divergence threshold.

PPO is simpler to implement than natural gradients and TRPO, requiring no constraint-based programs or second-order derivatives. Instead, it's update can be just performed using popular stochastic gradient descent algorithms like ADAM (drastically decreasing run time), and adjust the penalty when updates are too large or too small.

In summary, PPO is much easier to work with than TRPO, while being

competitive and often even outperforming it.

4.4.2 Variant with clipped objective

Clipped PPO is typically the term PPO is associated with in general. It usually outperforms the penalty-based variant and is simpler to implement.

Rather than changing penalties over time, the range within which the policy can change is being restricted. As advantages achieved by updates outside the clipping range are not used for updating purposes, it can provide a method to stay relatively close to the existing policy. The objective function still depends on the surrogate advantage:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\pi_{\theta}}^{CLIP}(\pi_{\theta_k}) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi_{\theta}} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T [\min(\rho_t(\pi_{\theta}, \pi_{\theta_k}) A_t^{\pi_{\theta_k}}, \text{clip}(\rho_t(\pi_{\theta}, \pi_{\theta_k}), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) A_t^{\pi_{\theta_k}})] \right], \quad (52)$$

here, ρ_t is the importance sampling ratio

$$\rho_t(\pi_{\theta}, \pi_{\theta_k}) = \frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_k}(a_t | s_t)}, \quad (53)$$

and the 'clip' function means that the importance sampling ratio needs to be between $1 - \epsilon$ and $1 + \epsilon$, and t means we are at timestep t .

The terms $(1 - \epsilon)A$ and $(1 + \epsilon)A$ do not depend on θ , therefore here the gradient becomes 0. Consequently, samples outside the trusted region are not taken into consideration, discouraging overly large updates. As a result, the policy update itself won't be explicitly constrained. As before, an optimizer like ADAM can be simply used to perform the updates.

To achieve the desired behavior ϵ should be tuned serving as an implicit restriction on KL divergence. In practice, $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.2$ are values that work well. These values drift a bit from the theoretical foundations of natural policy gradients, but empirically it works well. For details, see Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 PPO with Clipped Objective

- 1: **Input:** initial policy parameters θ_0 , clipping threshold ϵ
- 2: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2 \dots$ **do**
- 3: Collect set of partial trajectories \mathcal{D}_k on policy $\pi_k = \pi(\theta_k)$
- 4: Estimate advantages $A_t^{\pi_k}$ using any advantage estimation algorithm
- 5: Compute policy update

$$\theta_{k+1} = \arg \max_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\theta_k}^{CLIP}(\theta)$$

- 6: by taking K steps of minibatch SGD (via Adam), where

$$\mathcal{L}_{\theta}^{CLIP}(\pi_{\theta_k}) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi_{\theta}} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T [\min(\rho_t(\theta) A_t^{\pi_{\theta_k}}, \text{clip}(\rho_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) A_t^{\pi_{\theta_k}})] \right]$$

Remark: PPO2 (Schulman et al., 2017) is a well known term in the field of reinforcement learning. Fortunately, PPO2 is simply an updated version of the algorithm released by OpenAI. When directly using the OpenAI implementation, it’s good to remember that PPO2 is a better version than the simple PPO.

5 Hierarchical model for building a tower

This section focuses on how to develop a hierarchical reinforcement learning model (Wulfmeier et al., 2019), (Sutton and Barto, 1998) for building a tower of cubes using a robotic arm in a simulated environment. This research utilizes the Robosuite environment (Zhu et al., 2020), which provides a realistic simulation platform for robotic manipulation tasks, see Körber et al. (2021) on comparing various simulation environments for robotic use. The goal is to train a robotic arm to perform the tower construction task by learning a set of subtasks, namely reach, grasp, and stack, using the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm.

The hierarchical reinforcement learning approach allows the robotic arm

to learn a hierarchy of skills, enabling it to perform complex tasks more efficiently. At the high-level, the arm learns how to plan and execute sequences of options, while at the low-level, it learns the policies within each option. The reach option allows the arm to move its end-effector to the target cube, the grasp option enables the arm to pick up the cube, and the stack option teaches the arm how to stack the cubes to build a tower.

5.1 Options

An option (Sutton and Barto, 1998) has a policy, π , and a state-dependent termination function, γ . To execute an option $\omega = \langle \pi_\omega, \gamma_\omega \rangle$ at time t , we determine the action a_t to take from the policy $\pi_\omega(\cdot|s_t)$, and then terminate at time $t + 1$ with probability $1 - \gamma_\omega(s_{t+1})$. If the option does not terminate there, then a_{t+1} is obtained from $\pi_\omega(\cdot|s_{t+1})$, and then the option terminates at time $t + 2$ with probability $1 - \gamma_\omega(s_{t+2})$, and so on until termination. It is obvious that the probability of ending the episode is fairly small far from the termination condition, and if being closer, the probability becomes higher.

I consider low-level actions to be special cases of options. Each action a comes from an option $\langle \pi_\omega, \gamma_\omega \rangle$ whose policy determines the action $\pi_\omega(s) = a$, and whose termination function is zero, $\gamma_\omega(s) = 0$. The agent can either select a low-level action, terminating after one time step, or select a larger option that might execute for more time steps before terminating.

Options are designed so that they are interchangeable with low-level actions. Also the notion of policy can be generalized to a hierarchical policy that selects from options rather than actions, where options, when selected, execute until termination. In the simplest case, the learning process ‘jumps’ from option initiation to option termination, with an update only occurring when an option terminates.

The conventional model of an action is the state-transition probabilities

and the expected reward for taking the action in each state. In the case of options the appropriate model is again of two parts, one corresponding to the state transition resulting from executing the option and one corresponding to the expected reward along the way. The reward part for an option model is similar to the expected reward for state-action pairs in general reinforcement learning:

$$r(s, \omega) = \mathbb{E} [R_1 + \gamma R_2 + \gamma^2 R_3 + \dots + \gamma^{\tau-1} R_\tau | S_0 = s, A_{0:\tau-1} \sim \pi_\omega, \tau \sim \gamma_\omega] \quad (54)$$

for all options ω and all states s , where τ represents the random time step where the option terminated according to γ_ω . Note that the discount factor γ is not related to the termination probabilities γ_ω .

Also, for an option ω we define the probability of ω starting in s and for possible termination state s' as

$$p(s'|s, \omega) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \gamma^k P\{S_k = s', \tau = k | S_0 = s, A_{0:k-1} \sim \pi_\omega, \tau \sim \gamma_\omega\}. \quad (55)$$

The factor γ^k indicates that this probability is no longer a transition probability. The above definition of the transition part of an option model allows it to formulate Bellman equations and dynamic programming algorithms that can be applied to all options, including low-level actions.

For example, the general Bellman equation for a hierarchical policy π is:

$$v_\pi(s) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega(s)} \pi(\omega|s) \left[r(s, \omega) + \sum_{s'} p(s'|s, \omega) v_\pi(s') \right], \quad (56)$$

where $\Omega(s)$ means the possible options at the state s . If $\Omega(s)$ is only the set of low-level actions, then this equation will be the usual Bellman equation version, except for γ included hidden in the new p . Similarly, the corresponding

planning algorithms would also have γ hidden in the formulas.

The value iteration algorithm with options for all $s \in S$ reads

$$v_{k+1}(s) = \max_{\omega \in \Omega(s)} \left[r(s, \omega) + \sum_{s'} p(s'|s, \omega) v_k(s') \right]. \quad (57)$$

If $\Omega(s)$ includes all the low-level actions available in every state s , then this algorithm converges to the conventional v^* , from which the optimal policy can be computed. However, it is particularly useful to plan with options when only a subset of the possible options are considered in $\Omega(s)$ in each state. Value iteration will then converge to the best hierarchical policy limited to the restricted set of options. Although this policy may be sub-optimal, convergence can be much faster because fewer options are considered and because each option can jump over many time steps.

To plan with options, the agent must either be given the option models, or learn them (e.g., Veeriah et al., 2021). For building a tower has some obvious tasks I would like to do (reach or grasp a cube, stack the cubes). So it's planned to give the agent the option models trained with PPO algorithm and proceed from that, but it is important to mention this options also could be the result of machine learning but that exceeds the limits of this thesis.

5.2 The subtasks of building a tower of cubes

I have three cubes in my environment, one red, one blue and one green. The final goal would be to build a tower of these cubes in the correspondent order. The PPO algorithm is employed to optimize the policy parameters of low-level policies. The desired outcomes of this research contribute to the advancement of robotic manipulation and reinforce the potential of hierarchical reinforcement learning for complex tasks.

As already mentioned, my goal was to make four different options for my

hierarchical model. The four options are ((inspired by Hundt et al., 2020):

- Pushing and reorienting cubes;
- Reaching a cube;
- Grasping the reached cube;
- Stacking by place the cube to the suitable place.

Although the goals and initial states are different for each task, they have the same environment and same state space. The state space includes where the cubes are, the exact position of the robot (joint angles, gripper orientation, gripper's openness in the joint space). The state also tells if a cube is grasped by the arm or not.

The action space can be described as how much each of the robot arm joints are rotated as an absolute not a relative angle, as well as and the gripper orientation. Therefore, the whole action space is available all the time. The Panda robot has seven degrees of freedom, six for joint rotations and one for the orientation of the gripper.

The difference between the option environments are only their reset and reward functions. The grasping option can only begin for example if the cube is sufficiently close to the end-effector.

For the four options I will need termination conditions as I discussed in the previous section. Possible termination conditions can be the followings:

- Sweeping when the cubes are far enough from each other;
- Reaching if the target cube and end-effector are close enough to each other;
- Grasping the target cube if reachable;
- Stacking the grasped cube stable on the base cube.

Figure 7: Reach task accomplished by the simulated robot using PPO algorithm.

Figure 8: Progress evaluation of “Reach” tasks that is showing an overall improvement during the training sessions with 1.5 million time steps, evaluated in every 20000 step. **Left:** Mean episode length, where the maximum length is set to 1000. **Right:** Mean episodic reward during evaluation. The scale is not absolute, trends are meaningful, however.

Here I only present the subtask of reaching a cube. For this specific subtask the reward function was straightforward. When the end-effector is getting closer to the cube I give a positive reward in the function of the distance, similarly if it is getting away from the object than I can give a negative reward for that. I also give some additional reward if the task's termination condition is met - during the training termination can also occur when the program just reached a number of timesteps (currently with value 1000).

The training process is evaluated in Fig. 8 and the succeeded task with the learned policy is shown in Fig. 7.

Due to the time constraints, the other PPO models are only going to be made in the future.

6 Conclusions and outlook

In the first half of the thesis, I described how to grasp on object with a physical robotic arm owned by SZTAKI, the QArm. The task turns more difficult if the target object to be caught is not a fixed sized and colored ball. Currently, the arm is only trained to grasp a specific ball. Later, to grasp different objects with the arm, the problem might require an additional camera. This is necessary because of the limitations of the built-in depth camera, since the depth measurement accuracy is guaranteed only when the object is out of reach for the robotic arm.

The second half of the thesis focused on training robotic arms to carry out more complex tasks, such as the building of a tower of cubes. The training was proposed with the help of a hierarchic reinforcement learning algorithm in a virtual simulation environment. I showed how a complex task can be divided into lower level subtasks simplifying the problem at hand, and I presented the training of one sub-task.

After completing the training of policies of each subtask as well as the training of the hierarchical policy, I have to transform the virtual environment to the real world. To achieve this, the first task is to create a realistic virtual model of the physical QArm. This involves accurately representing the arm's kinematics, dynamics, and sensor capabilities within the virtual environment. Although these are given in a separated environment, it remains challenging to transfer the operations to another environment.

The virtual model should closely match the physical QArm to enable seamless transfer of the trained policies. After the virtual QArm has been successfully trained, the next step is to transfer the learned policies to the physical QArm. It may involve fine-tuning the policies through additional training.

Additionally, future research can explore methods to further enhance the performance and generalization capabilities of the hierarchical reinforcement learning model. This may involve more dynamic environments, for example with moving obstacles.

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